

Improving Tribological Properties of Chemically Modified Mahua Oil-Lubricant oil blends with MWCNT nanoparticles

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Abstract— A significant portion of the power generated by internal combustion engines is lost due to friction, primarily caused by the numerous moving components. Mineral-based lubricant oils, derived from petroleum, contribute to environmental pollution, pose disposal challenges, and their continuous use accelerates crude oil depletion. To address these concerns, this study investigates the incorporation of non-edible mahua bio lubricant oil blended with commercial lubricant oil and non-metallic, carbon-based Multi walled carbon nanoparticles (MWCNTs) as a bio-based lubricant-nano composite. The study evaluates the physio-chemical and tribological properties of an aluminum pin against a high-carbon steel disc using a wear testing machine under varying loads (20, 35, and 50N) while maintaining a fixed speed (900 rpm) and radial distance (3000 m). A blend containing 10% mahua bio lubricant oil and 90% 20W40 commercial oil is designated as B10. Additionally, CNT nanoparticles are introduced into B10 at concentrations of 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75 mg/l, labeled as B10+0.25%, B10+0.5%, and B10+0.75%, respectively. The results indicate that the nano-enhanced blends exhibit stability, with their physio-chemical properties aligning with American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standards. At higher loads, the B10+0.25% sample demonstrates reductions of 43.10% in the Coefficient of Friction (COF), 70.36% in wear rate, 33% in wear loss, and 46% in frictional force compared to 20W40 commercial oil. These findings highlight the potential of MWCNTs as sustainable additives for mahua-based bio-lubricants, enhancing their performance in wear testing applications.

KEYWORDS—MAHUA OIL, BIO-LUBRICANTS, TRIBOLOGICAL PERFORMANCE PROPERTIES, WEAR, COEFFICIENT OF FRICTION.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tribology is made up of two Greek words; “tribos” and “logos,” the former means “rubbing,” while the latter means “word.” Tribology, in practice, is the science of controlling and managing wear, friction, and lubrication; in practice, it is the science of controlling and managing wear, friction, and lubrication [1]. Wear and friction in systems are some of the major reasons for the failure of machinery in engines, gears, bearings, etc., all of which are vital for the smooth operation of mechanical systems in various industries, including automotive, aerospace, mining, and machinery, and energy loss, which is an important tribological issue arising from high friction [2]. To overcome the aforementioned issue, the most effective approach is to lubricate the machinery. Lubricants are broadly used in industry and manufacturing units to protect products and tools from wear and to maintain their respective surface qualities. Moreover, lubricants optimize the coefficient of friction (COF) of the fabrication processes and excess heat accumulation in mechanical systems. As a result, the enhancement of lubricant oil properties is of great importance in the context of protecting machinery from highly probable damage and decreasing energy consumption [3]. In industrial machines, friction and wear lead to energy loss and material waste, necessitating proper control. When mechanical components in relative motion come into contact, friction arises, dissipates energy, and reduces the efficiency of mechanical devices[4], approximately 50% of the fuel energy is lost to friction in internal combustion engines. Diesel and vegetable oil fuel mixtures improve lubrication, considering that approximately 40-50% of all energy lost through internal engine friction is due to piston ring-cylinder friction. This agrees with Gil et al. [5], In recent years, automobile engine manufacturers have been facing major problems related to the compatibility of automotive

components with bio-diesel and its blends. Biodiesel usage is expected to increase because of the few disadvantages of fossil fuels, such as their depletion and environmental degradation. Conventional petroleum diesel is partially or completely replaced by biodiesel. The recent challenges to be considered with biodiesel are the tribo-corrosion instability of its properties due to exposure to different metals and other environmental factors. These issues affect a concern towards the tribological compatibility of automotive materials in biodiesel and its blends [1–5]. Additives and mahua bio-oil blends such as B10 exhibit lower frictional forces than conventional lubricants. Another crucial characteristic of bio lubricants is their longevity compared with that of other petroleum derivatives. However, the disposal of lubricant residues requires responsibility because of their resistance to biodegradation, especially for fossil-based oil lubricants [6]. Lubricant additives, in a few weight percent, are added to the base stock to completely enhance the lubricate characteristics. They are essential for maintaining the overall performance of lubricants and are capable of manipulating particular features such as friction and wear, clotting, oxidation, foaming, and corrosion tendency [3]. Nanoparticles added to lubricants reduce energy loss, improve the life of machine elements, and protect the environment by reducing friction and wear [7]. In addition, bio-oil has higher viscosity and solvency (dissolving power) properties than petro-diesel. A higher percentage of bio-oil in commercial oil blends causes an increase in viscosity, which increases filter plugging, injector coking, moving parts sticking, etc., which triggers chemical reactivity for corrosion of metals, changes its oil composition, and consequently results in the degradation of oil properties [8]. Fazal [9] investigated the corrosion rate of metals (copper, leaded bronze, and phosphorus bronze) in contact with 100% palm biodiesel, with and without the addition of additives (tert-butylamine). Metal surface degradation was significantly reduced in the presence of additives. The presence of additives in bio-oil reduces the corrosion rate of the tested metals, thereby increasing the material suitability. This indicates that the corrosiveness of palm biodiesel can be significantly reduced by the addition of additives. Nano-additives are new lubricant additives that were recently introduced to the industry. Some of the advantages of using nano-additives include a suitable size to enter contact asperities, thermal stability, variety of particle chemistries, and reaction rate with the surface without an induction period, which is an important factor for conventional lubricant additives [10–13]. Over the past decades, many studies have stated that the addition of nanoparticles, such as metals, metal oxides, metal sulphides, carbonates, borates, carbon materials, organic materials, and rare-earth compounds, to lubricants is effective in decreasing both friction and wear. The friction-reduction and anti-wear behaviors are improved by the individual features of nanoparticles, such as their size, shape, and physico-chemical nature [14]. Based on the literature survey, Biobased lubricants derived from vegetable oils with commercial lubricant oil offer good lubricity, higher viscosity index, higher flash point, and good anti-wear properties as compared with conventional lubricants [2]. The nanoparticles addition in bio lubricants or bio-commercial based lubricant oil blends further enhances the tribological behavior of oils. The enhancement in friction-reducing and anti-wear properties is attributed to the unique characteristics of the nanoparticles, including their size, shape, physico-chemical, and thermal properties [15]. No research is found with the addition of carbon based nanoparticles such as Mutiwalled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs) in modified Modified oil (mahua oil based)-commercial lubricant blends to improve the physio-chemical and tribological properties. Hence, this current study focuses on improving the tribological properties of modified Modified oil-commercial lubricant oil blends with nanoparticles dispersion.

A. Novelty of the current Study

A review of the literature indicates that bio-based lubricants derived from non-edible oils blended with commercial lubricant oils exhibit superior lubricity, a higher viscosity index, an elevated flash point, and improved anti-wear properties compared to conventional lubricants. The addition of nanoparticles (CNTs) to bio-lubricants or bio-commercial lubricant blends further enhances their tribological performance. This improvement in friction reduction and anti-wear characteristics is primarily due to the unique properties of CNTs, including their size, shape, physicochemical attributes, and thermal behavior. However, no research has been identified on the incorporation of carbon-based nanoparticles, such as Multi walled carbon nano particles (CNTs), into raw mahua bio lubricant oil-commercial lubricant blends to enhance their physio-chemical and tribological properties. Therefore, the present study aims to enhance the tribological performance of raw oil-commercial lubricant oil blends through NP dispersion.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Madhuca longifolia, commonly known as Mahua, Butter Tree, Iluppai, or Ippa-chettu, is a tropical tree native to India, Nepal, Myanmar, and Sri Lanka. It belongs to the Sapotaceae family and thrives in arid environments, primarily in tropical mixed deciduous forests across Indian states such as Maharashtra, Odisha, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Kerala, Gujarat, West Bengal, and Tamil Nadu.

This fast-growing tree reaches 20 m and has evergreen or semi-evergreen foliage. It takes four to seven years to mature and produces edible fruits containing one to two kidney-shaped kernels. This tree has significant economic and ecological value, particularly for non-edible oil production, with a potential yield of 60 million tons per year in India. Mahua kernels contain 50% oil, The free fatty acids content in the mahua oil is shown in Table 1. Additionally, n-hexane (99%), SPAN80, and Mutiwalled Carbon Nanotubes are provided by platoninc nanotech pvt. Ltd, Jharkhand.

A. Fatty acid determination

The fatty acid profile of the oil has been calculated in accordance with the standard EN14,103. The functional properties of Mahua oil were analysed by gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy apparatus with a capillary tube of 30 mm long and 0.25 mm in diameter equipped with 0.25 μm Rextex. Samples were inoculated in a flipped/section flow ratio of 24:1. Helium has been used as a gas stream with a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Infusion kept constant at 70°C for 1 h in a water bath. Within 1 h, the solution was incubated into a distinct funnel to segregate between FAME and glycerol. The dense liquid that was glycerol would stay at the bottom, while FAME remained at the upper edge. The glycerol was then removed and FAME is gone through a washing process to remove an excessive acid. This process was conducted by pouring hot water into FAME in the separating funnel. The mixture was left overnight in an oven at a temperature of 120°C to remove excessive methanol and water content. Finally, to develop bio-lubricant, FAME evolved the next step of transesterification with TMP ester at a ratio of 3.5:1. The reaction was conducted in 500 ml three-neck flask provided with a thermometer, sampling port and Graham condenser. The three-neck flask was plunged into the oil bath at the temperature of 120°C. The FAME and TMP were poured into the three-neck flask and heated gradually up to 120°C. The magnetic temperature and oven temperature were kept at 250°C (programmed to begin at 120°C, kept at this temperature for 5 min and heated at a rate of 3°C/min to 250°C). The total yield of free fatty acid was determined by off-line GC-MS using a modified EN-14103 procedure.

The amount of saturated fatty acids is less in amount so, to make this oil feasible for lubrication purpose, chemical modification is required.

TABLE 1
PRESENTS THE FREE FATTY ACIDS OF MAHUA OIL

Sl. No.	Fatty Acid	Percentage
1	Palmitic(C16:0)	19.2
2	Stearic(C18:0)	23.4
3	Oleic(C18:1)	58.6
4	Linolenic acid(C18:2)	12.4
5	Arachidic acid(C20:0)	2.1

B. Chemical modification of mahua oil

Chemical modification of mahua oil, such as through epoxidation, enhances its properties for applications like lubrication, biodiesel production, and coatings, improving viscosity, viscosity index, and tribological characteristics. The conversion of mahua oil involves three distinct chemical alteration phases. First, the free fatty acid content of the oil needed to be reduced using the titration technique to drop below 1%. Using phenolphthalein as an indicator, the unprocessed mahua oil was dissolved in a solution of sodium hydroxide and methanol. A single gram of heated oil, 50 mL of propyl alcohol, and multiple phenolphthalein droplets were combined in a conical jar as a part of the technique, which required heating the oil to 70°C. This step culminated in the dropwise addition of NaOH until the solution took on a rose-colored hue.

The subsequent phase focused on generating fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) via an alkali-catalyzed transesterification approach. The transformation was performed in a specialized three-neck flask equipped with a Graham condenser. FAME and methanol were combined in a 6:1 molar ratio and submerged in a water bath, while 1% sodium hydroxide was incorporated to enhance the reactivity between the constituents. Throughout a 60-minute interval at a constant temperature of 70°C, the mixture underwent transformation, after which it was transferred to a separation apparatus to isolate the FAME from glycerol. The denser glycerol component settled at the bottom, thus facilitating its removal. The FAME was subsequently cleansed with heated water to eliminate residual acidic elements and subjected to thermal treatment overnight at 120°C to extract the surplus methanol and aqueous content.

The final transformation into a bio-lubricant necessitated an additional transesterification process involving FAME and TMP ester at a 3.5:1 ratio. This reaction was conducted in a 500 ml three-neck flask outfitted with thermal monitoring equipment, sampling access, and a condensation apparatus. The vessel was immersed in an oil bath maintained at 120°C into which FAME and TMP were introduced and gradually heated. Magnetic agitation ensured thorough integration of the solutions, while sodium methoxide functioned as a catalytic agent. The reaction proceeded for a duration of five hours, ultimately yielding the desired biolubricant compound through complete chemical transformation. The folw chart of current study in the Fig 1.

Figure 1. Presents the flow chart of methodology

C. Sample preparation for the test

Modified Mahua bio lubricant oil is blended with conventional 20W40 lubricant oil at a 10:90 volume ratio, forming a B10 blend. To enhance stability, Carbon Nanotube (MWCNT) were incorporated at concentrations of 0.25 mg/l, 0.5, and 0.75 mg/l. These MWCNTs were surface-modified using a lipophilic nonionic SPAN80 surfactant in a 1:4 ratio (MWCNTs:SPAN80), with n-hexane as the dispersing agent. After mixing, n-hexane was evaporated and the treated MWCNTs at a dosage of 0.25, 0.50, and 0.75 mg/l were dispersed in the B10 (10% Modified mahua bio lubricant oil in 90% of 20W40 lubricant oil) blend to improve stability, use a water bath and a probe sonicator (Hielscher Ultrasonic UP400S, 160 W, 40 kHz) at a frequency of 40 kHz for half an hour, resulting in B10+0.25%, B10+0.5%, and B10+0.75%. Lubricant oil, Modified Mahua oil, B10, nanoparticles (at dosages of 0.25, 0.50, and 0.75 ppm), and IN bio-lubricant blends are tested on a Pin on Disc Wear Testing Machine (NOVUS TRIBO SOLUTIONS MAKE) using standard testing parameters of 900 rpm, radial distance of 3000 m, and loads of 20, 35, and 50 N. The proposed lubricant sample's test matrix is mentioned in Table 2. The preparation of oil samples with nanoparticles are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Presents the preparation of oil samples using probe sonicator a) ultrasonication of nano lubricant blends, b) Modified mahua bio lubricant and lubricant oil (20W40), and c) Prepared samples.

TABLE 2

PROPOSED TEST MATRIX AND TEST CONDITIONS

Sl. No.	Prepared Samples	NP- Dosage (mg/l)	Modified Oil (ml)	Lub oil (ml)
1	Lubricant Oil	-	-	1000
2	Modified Mahua Oil	-	1000	-
3	B10	-	100	900
4	B10+0.25 mg/l	0.25	100	900
5	B10+0.50 mg/l	0.5	100	900
6	B10+0.75 mg/l	0.75	100	900

C. Characterization of MWCNT nanoparticles

Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs) with a purity greater than 99% were obtained from Platonic Nanotech. A field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) was used to examine the material by scanning it with a focused electron beam, generating images based on interactions between electrons and the sample's atoms[26]. These interactions produce various signals that provide insights into the surface topography and composition of the material[27]. The FESEM image, shown in Figure 3 (a), reveals that the MWCNTs have an average diameter ranging from 10 to 15 nm and a length between 5 and 15 μm and other properties are mentioned in Table.3. MWCNTs serve as effective fuel additives, improving the quality of fuel samples. The morphology of MWCNT nano-additives was further analyzed using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) (Model: JEM-2100F, FEG TEM, 200 kV TEM). The HRTEM image, depicted in Figure 3(b), illustrates MWCNT bundles with smooth surfaces.

Fig.3 (a) FE -SEM Images of MWCNTs nanotubes at magnification level of 300000x (b) HR- TEM Image of MWCNTs at 50nm

TABLE 3

ILLUSTRATES THE PROPERTIES OF MWCNT NANOPARTICLES

Item	Description
Item Description Supplier	Platonic Nanotech pvt ltd
Average size of nanoplates	5–20 nm thickness, length 2-10 μ m
Thermal conductivity	6000 watts/m-k
Mechanical tensile modulus	1-2 Tpa
Surface area (SSA)	250–270 m ² /g
Density	0.06-0.09 g/cm ³
Purity	>99%
Appearance	Black

E. Materials of Pin on Disk Apparatus

Aluminium is a low-density material that can resist corrosion due its surface passivation. Aluminium is also a relatively soft, durable, lightweight, ductile, and malleable metal [21, 22]. This material was thus applied a the piston material facing the maximum friction with hardness of 98 HRB. This material can also resist wear and corrosion. For the disc, high carbon steel was used as it offers high hardness (65 HRC) and wear resistance. The pin was cylindrically shaped by turning on a lathe. One end of the pin was made flat to ensure a position for contact with the disc. The pin had a diameter of 6 mm and length of 30 mm. The pin was further polished using emery paper with grit sizes of 200, 400 600, and 1200 nm before performing the experiment on the machine.

F. Test Set Up

The lubricity of a fluid is a key property influencing the friction and wear characteristics of interacting surfaces. To assess lubricant performance, a pin-on-disc tribometer is used to analyze the tribological behavior of prepared samples following the ASTM G99 standard, as investigated by Nassef et al. [16]. Figure 4. illustrates the pin-on-disc test equipment, while Figure 5. presents a schematic diagram of the pin on disc.

Across all test conditions, the sliding speed was maintained at 900 rpm, and the sliding distance was set at 3000 m. A total of 50 ml of lubricant was supplied throughout the test, following the specified conditions. After each test, the pins were removed from the

apparatus, cleaned with acetone, and dried with tissue paper to absorb any remaining lubricant, which was later used for surface analysis. The applied loads of 20, 35, and 50 N were manually controlled, while the lubricant was consistently applied to the wear disc to ensure complete coverage at the contact interface between the aluminum pin and the high-carbon steel wear disc. The experiments were conducted on the prepared oil samples under various conditions to evaluate the coefficient of friction, wear rate, frictional force, and wear loss. The controlled test parameters are listed in Table 4. Wear scar imaging was performed using a Metzer optical microscope, with the average scar size determined from three separate observations. To measure the material's wear rate, the pin's weight was recorded before and after testing using a precision balance machine. Prior to weighing, the pin was cleaned with acetone to ensure accurate measurements.

TABLE 4
THE TEST PARAMETERS DURINT THE EXPERIMENT

Sl. No.	Parameter	Value
1	Load(N)	20,35,50
2	Sliding Speed(rpm)	900
3	Sliding Distance(m)	3000
4	Time(sec)	920
5	Track Diameter(mm)	35

Fig. 4. Shows the experimental setup of Pin on Disc.

Fig. 5. Schematic lay out of Pin on disc Wear testing Apparatus.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Physicochemical properties characterisation

The Kinematic viscosity was assessed using a Saybolt's viscometer according to the ASTM D-445 standard at atmospheric pressure and temperatures of 40 °C and 100 °C. by using Eq.1. The test was conducted three times, and the mean value was used to reduce the error and ensure reliability. The flash point and fire point of the oil were measured by using Cleveland open-cup Apparatus according to ASTM D-92 respectively. The Density of oil was measured using a Hydrometer standardized as per ASTM E2995-14 at atmospheric pressure and room temperature[17]. The Viscosity Index of all prepared samples was measured using a Redwood Viscometer, following the ASTM D2270 standard, with the formula for Viscosity Index calculation given in Eq. 2. The tribological properties were analysed at Metro Composite Testing Lab, Chennai, India. The obtained data for Modified lubricant, Modified mahua bio lubricant, and Modified bio-lubricant with nanoparticles are presented in the Table 5.

$$\text{Viscosity} = At - \frac{B}{t} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where, A = 0.264, and B = 190 when t = 40 to 85 Sec

A = 0.247, and B = 65 when, t = 85-2000 Sec

$$\text{Viscosity Index} = \frac{L-H}{L-U} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Where, L = Kinematic Viscosity of Commercial Lubricating oil at 40°C,

H = Kinematic Viscosity of a Reference Commercial Lubricating oil at 40 °C,

U = Kinematic Viscosity of Prepared Same at 40 °C.

TABLE 5

PRESENTS THE PHYSIO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TESTED LUBRICANT SAMPLES WITH NANO PARTICLE ADDITIONS.

Properties/Test ed Samples	ASTM Standard with limits	Commercial Lubricant Oil	Chemically Modified Bio-Lubricant	B10	B10+0.25%	B10+0.5%	B10+0.75%
Density@26°C (g/ml)	D5002 (0.75-0.95)	0.880	0.892	0.885	0.887	0.892	0.897
Kinematic Viscosity (mm ² /sec)	D445 (10-100 Cst at 40°C)	130	22	90	93	95	98
	2-25Cst at 100°C	14.9	8.2	12.8	13.2	13.6	14
Flash Point @°C	D92->200	200	160	172	178	182	185
Fire Point	D92	204	165	176	182	186	190
Viscosity Index	D2270(90-110)	105	95	97	100	102	104

B. Tribological Properties

1. Coefficient of Friction (COF) Analysis:

Fig. 6. Illustrates the Coefficient of Friction vs. Time for the tested lubricant samples at different loads a) 20 N, b) 30 N, and c) 50 N

The coefficient of friction (COF) is essential for minimizing friction, which lowers the pace at which metal components deteriorate and extends engine life. It also absorbs heat from the engine parts and lessens noise. Fig. 6 shows the COF vs. Time for the tested lubricating oil samples under different loads (20, 35, and 50 N). Figure 6 (a) Illustrates the COF results for dry condition (without lubrication) rise (0.2625, 0.3630, and 0.3310) when the load increases. Additionally, because of their comparable density and viscosity characteristics, the samples of Modified mahua oil and commercial lubricant oil (20W40, which is frequently used for four-wheeler vehicles), has lower COF values approximately 0.11. Moreover, the sample B10 results in reduced COF values 0.070, 0.083, and 0.105 at different load conditions 20, 35, and 50 N respectively as depicted in 6 a, b, and c. Nevertheless, the nanoparticles dispersed B10 samples at a dosage of (0.25, 0.50, and 0.75 mg/l) results in reduced COF 0.05 to 0.9 with reference to the running time. The decreased COF values are found to be 0.0631, 0.0485, and 0.0443 for B10+0.25, B10+0.5, and B10+0.75 samples respectively at 920 sec running time of the pin on the disc to cover 3000 m at full load condition (50N) as shown in Fig. 6c. The maximum COF is lowered by 86.61, and 43.10% for B10+0.75 sample when compared to Dry condition and commercial lubricant 20W40 sample. The reduced COF is due to the improved viscosity, density, and Viscosity Index at high concentration of nanoparticles while, the minimal dosage of nanoparticles tend to nanoparticles effect on the anti-wear property depends on the proper dispersion of the particles in the lubricant. The MWCNT nanoparticles are having the capability to gets properly dispersed in the solution due to the optimized MWCNTs to surfactant ratio which promotes anti-wear mechanism. The reduction in values can be attributed to improved stability, increased surface area, and enhanced lubricity, resulting from the uniform dispersion of nanoparticles and the formation of a sufficiently thick lubricant film. Additionally, the nanoparticles fill the microscopic gaps on the disc surface,

creating a smoother surface and ensuring effective lubrication. This process promotes a rolling mechanism rather than sliding friction, thereby minimizing wear on the disc surface[1]. Consequently, the nano dispersion in the B10 sample plays a crucial role in reducing wear[18,19].

2. Wear rate Analysis:

Fig. 7. Illustrates the Wear Rate vs. Time for the tested lubricant samples at different loads a) 20 N, b) 30 N, and c) 50 N.

When a pin slides against a disc under an applied stress, friction causes material to be lost from the disc's surface at a rate known as the wear rate. Fig. 7 a, b, and c show the wear rate for the tested lubricating oil samples at various loads (20, 35, and 50 N) throughout a running period of 920 seconds and a radial distance of 3000 m. It is noticed from the figures 7a, b, and c that the wear rate is tremendously high (95.49, 99.86, and 646.33 microns) for dry condition at all loads when compared to other samples. Moreover, the Modified mahua bio lubricant oil possesses higher wear (25.93, 31.46, and 32.52 microns) as correlated to commercial lubricant oil sample (20.85, 19.60, and 28.21 microns) at different load conditions. Further, the MWCNT nanoparticles dispersed bio-lubricant B10 blends reduced wear to a maximum extent (5.98, 5.06, and 8.36 microns) at 20, 35, and 50 N loads for B10+0.75% bio-lubricant sample. The wear rate is greatly reduced by 93.73, 94.90, and 98.7% for B10+0.75% sample when compared to dry condition at 20, 35, and 50 N loads. Similarly, the wear rate is well decreased by 71.3, 74.16, and 70.36% for B10+0.75% blend as compared to commercial lubricant oil at 20, 35, and 50 N loads. The anti-wear qualities of the lubricating oil sample that was created with MWCNT nano additions are what caused the decrease in wear rate. Because MWCNTs in base lubricant oil are more stable and uniform because the dispersion of nanoparticles with surfactant causing adhesive bonding between MWCNTs to base lubricant oils. Furthermore, because of the nanoparticles' capacity to disperse in base oil samples without sedimentation at high concentrations and their surface adsorption to promote anti-wear properties, the MWCNT contained bio-lubricant sample at high dosage decreased the wear rate [20]. The amount of nanoparticles are insufficient to produce rolling action between the aluminum pin and high carbon steel wear surfaces, further, the addition of MWCNTs at higher dosage could improve the viscosity and result in adsorption on the disc surface.

3. Wear loss Analysis:

In pin-on-disc testing, wear loss is the amount of material removed from the pin or disc due to sliding wear. This is measured as a change in weight or volume and is crucial for determining material wear resistance. Fig. 8 shows the wear loss Vs. load graphs for all tested materials, including dry condition, 20W40, Modified mahua bio-lubricant oil, B10 (bio-lubricant), and B10 with MWCNT nano additions at 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75% dose. The figure clearly shows that the wear loss is greatest (0.02, 0.03, and 0.17g) in dry conditions since there is no lubrication fluid between the surfaces. While modified mahua oil reduced wear to 0.01, 0.01, and 0.01g, this was attributable to the oil sample's high viscosity when compared to the dry state under three distinct loads. In contrast, the commercial lubricant reduced wear loss to 0.01, 0.01, and 0.01g at various weights. Furthermore, the B10 sample had lower wear loss than the other three samples, which was due to the sample's enhanced physiochemical characteristics. Furthermore, the nano-assisted B10 sample significantly reduced the wear rate to 0.01 at all loads for the B10+0.75% sample. The highest reduction in wear rate is around 88.23, with 33% for the B10+0.75% sample in dry conditions and the 20W40 sample in full load conditions. The reduced wear loss is attributable to the mending and rolling action of MWCNTs in the sample, the anti-wear capabilities of nano assisted-bio-commercial lubricant blends, and the sample B10+0.75% is found to be a promising and sustainable nano assisted bio-lubricant sample[1,21].

Fig.8. Wear loss vs Loads for the tested samples.

4. Friction force Analysis

Frictional force in the pin-on-disc device is the force that prevents the pin from moving relative to the revolving disc surface with which it makes contact. This force is generated by the interaction of two surfaces and is influenced by a variety of factors including materials, normal load, speed, and lubrication. The frictional force vs load for various lubricant samples are illustrated in Fig. 9. The graph clearly shows that the frictional force increases as the load increases, and the frictional force is found to be higher for dry conditions (5, 13, and 16.5N) as compared to other samples. Furthermore, the Modified mahua oil, 20W40, and B10 samples' frictional force is continuously reducing as their viscosity and lubricity properties increase. At higher loads, MWCNTs-dispersed B10 samples reduced frictional force to 0.52, 1.03, and 1.90N for B10+0.75% samples, respectively. The frictional force is reduced by 89, 91, and 88% for the B10+0.75% sample as compared to the dry state. While the frictional force is reduced by 84.7, 69, and 46% for the identical sample (B10+0.75%) when compared to the commercial lubricant. This

frictional reduction is achieved through the synergistic properties of bio-lubricant and MWCNTs. The bio-lubricant sample and nano-included bio-lubricant sample improve lubrication qualities, and MWCNTs are fully filled on the fine gaps of the disc surface, resulting in a mending and rolling mechanism and reduced frictional force [22]. Thus, further causing polishing with nanoparticles and lead to form protective layer or film with nano-bio-lubricant blend.

Fig. 9. Friction Force vs Load for the tested samples

5. Worn surface analysis

Worn surface analysis is the study of surface degradation and material loss caused by mechanical contact. It is widely used in tribology (the study of friction, wear, and lubrication) to better understand wear mechanisms and improve material performance. The Metzer optical microscope is used to photograph the worn surface of the pin material, as depicted in Figure 10. As shown in Fig. 10 (a), the worn surface of the pin material contains several grooves that have been cut in depth due to a lack of lubrication coating between the pin and the disc surface. Furthermore, the microscopic image Fig 10 (b) depicts the worn surface of the pin for a 20W40 oil sample, indicating reduced deep grooves and the number of pit holes. The addition of 0.75 mg/l MWCNTs to the B10 sample lowered the coefficient of friction, wear rate, wear loss, and friction force. As a result, Fig. 10 (c) shows the minimum range of grooves with no pit holes. The reduced grooves and pit holes are attributable to MWCNTs' improved stability in base oil samples, increased viscosity, and rolling action of MWCNTs in the gaps between the pin and disc surfaces[20,23]. While high concentrations of MWCNTs tend to stability, resulting in reduction of wear and friction[24,25].

Fig. 10. Metzer microscopic images of pin in Wear test a) Dry condition b) Commercial lubricant oil (20W40), and c) B10+0.25% sample.

IV.CONCLUSIONS

The current work aims to improve the tribological features of Modified mahua bio oil-commercial lubricant oil mixtures with MWCNT dispersion. The coefficient of friction, wear rate, wear loss, and wear scar image are significant factors for analyzing the tribological qualities of lubricating oil, which improves engine performance while also increasing engine life. Modified Mahua bio oil, commercial lubricant oil 20W40, B10, and MWCNTs (0.25, 0.50, 0.75%) in B10 samples were created and analyzed for physiochemical and tribological properties using a pin-on-disc equipment. The findings are compared to dry conditions with no lubrication oil and commercial lubricant oil as a standard reference. The following conclusions are derived from the preceding findings and discussions:

- The nano-assisted lubricating oil samples are shown to be stable at high concentrations, as evidenced by FESEM and HRTEM, and the physiochemical parameters of generated samples are reported to be within ASTM requirements.
- The COF dropped by 86.1 and 43.10% in the B10+0.75% sample compared to the dry condition and 20W40 sample at full load. This is attributed to the stability of MWCNTs in B10, enhanced viscosity, and the creation of a nano lubricant coating on worn surfaces.
- Wear rate increases with load, although it is found to be reduced by 98.7 and 70.36% for the B10+0.25% blend when compared to the dry condition and 20W40 sample. As the concentration of MWCNTs increases, the samples tend to agglomerate and settle after 24 hours, causing stability concerns.
- Additionally, using a higher dosage of MWCNTs distributed in B10 reduces friction-related wear loss. The mending, polishing and rolling mechanism and enhanced viscosity index resulted in a maximum reduction in wear loss of 88.3 and 33% when compared to the dry condition and 20W40 sample under higher loads, respectively.
- Further, the friction force decreases by 88 and 46% for the same sample compared to dry and commercial lubricant oil samples at high load condition, indicating a shift towards roller friction rather than sliding friction.
- Nevertheless, the worn scar image of a pin on dry condition is detected with high magnified deep blurs, whereas commercial lubricant oil indicates a reduced blur but pit holes are found. While the sample B10+0.75% displays fewer blurring and no pit holes, this indicates a lower wear rate, wear loss, and COF.
- The results are compared with dry conditions and commercial lubricant oil. The B10 sample containing nanoparticles at a high concentration shows promise as a more sustainable option for enhancing the tribological performance of the pin-on-disc apparatus and is recommended for use in internal combustion engine operations.

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